

Viscometric Study of Clay-humus Complexes

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Viscometric studies of clay-humus complexes have been made in the presence of different cations. The η_{sp}/C vs. C graphs are found to be linear, especially at high dilutions. An attempt has been made to obtain a rough idea about the molecular weights of the products of the reaction between clay and humus, using Staudinger's equation.

Clays are crystalline aggregates. Humic acid may perhaps be considered as mixtures of high polymers. Viscosity measurements have been undertaken with a view to obtain evidence of the interaction between clay and humic acid, if any. Myeres (*Soil Sci.*, 1937, **44**, 331) observed a considerable change in the time of flow of colloidal clay when it was mixed with organic colloidal sols; this change could not be explained by assuming simple mechanical mixing.

EXPERIMENTAL

An Ostwald viscometer in its simplest form was used. The time of flow of water at the temperature of experiment (30°) was 45 secs. Crude humic acid was extracted from Siliguri soil from Darjeeling, West Bengal by repeated treatment with $(N/2)Na_2CO_3$ solution. From the alkali leachate humic acid was coagulated by HCl (dil.) and finally purified by electro dialysis. The clay fractions ($<1\mu$) from four different soil samples were collected in the usual way. The clay suspension was then coagulated with HCl (dil.), thoroughly treated with H_2O_2 to destroy organic matter, and finally electro dialysed to obtain H-clay. The humic acid and clay fractions were mixed in the proportions of 1:60 in presence of different ions and about a week's time was allowed for the reaction to proceed. The time of flow of the different mixtures was measured in the same Ostwald viscometer at a constant temperature of 30° . The viscosities of different clay-humic acid mixtures in presence of metal and H^+ ions were measured with various amounts of solid matter present in the suspension and the values of specific viscosities were calculated. Similar viscosity data for clays in presence of different ions, but without humus, were also obtained for comparison with the above results. The variation of reduced viscosities of all the systems with dilution was followed graphically by plotting η_{sp}/C vs. C .

DISCUSSION

The viscosity of dilute suspensions of rigid spherical particles, which are wetted by the solvent, is given by Einstein's equation

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + 2.5\Phi + 4\Phi^2 + 5.3\Phi^3$$

Mathiolin A on treating with 80% H_2SO_4 (at 100° , for 2 hours) gave a demethoxylated compound as orange-red plates, m.p. 270° . (Found: C, 59.82; H, 3.50. $C_{15}H_{10}O_7$ requires C, 59.60; H, 3.31%).

The compound on distillation with zinc dust furnished a colorless compound (ethanol), m.p. 204° , which showed no depression on admixture with an authentic sample of 2-methylanthracene.

The studies carried out so far on mathiolin A indicates that the compound is an anthraquinone derivative, having four hydroxyl groups out of which three are phenolic in nature and the one, which escapes methylation, appears to be alcoholic in function. It also contains one OMe group.

Mathiolin B

Mathiolin B gave an orange-coloured solution with caustic alkalis, a greenish colour with H_2SO_4 (conc.), and a violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride. Its reaction with sodium bicarbonate indicated the presence of a carboxyl function in the molecule. Routine analysis of the compound showed the presence of one C-Me and OMe groups in the molecule.

With acetic anhydride-pyridine it formed a diacetate in yellow plates (glacial acetic acid), m.p. 176° . [Found: C, 61.02; H, 4.18; OAc, 20.32. $C_{21}H_{16}O_9$ requires C, 61.16; H, 3.88; OAc (for two), 20.87%].

The compound on methylation (in the similar manner as in case of mathiolin A) formed a monomethyl ether, m.p. 166° . (Found: C, 63.35; H, 4.18. $C_{18}H_{14}O_7$ requires C, 63.15; H, 4.09%) and a dimethyl ether, m.p. $152-53^\circ$. (Found: C, 64.26; H, 4.38. $C_{19}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 64.04; H, 4.49%).

Demethoxylation of mathiolin B with 80% H_2SO_4 (at 100° for 2 hours) gave orange-red plates (glacial acetic acid), m.p. 253° . [Found: C, 60.84; H, 3.36. $C_{16}H_{10}O_7$ requires C, 61.14; H, 3.18%].

Mathiolin B on distillation with zinc dust in a stream of hydrogen furnished colorless leaflets (ethanol), m.p., 205° , which showed no depression on admixture with an authentic sample of 2-methylanthracene.

The experimental data given above suggest that mathiolin B is also an anthraquinone derivative having a C-Me group in 2-position of the basic anthraquinone nucleus. It also contains a C-Me, a carboxyl and two phenolic hydroxyl groups in the molecule. Further study of these compounds is in progress.